

EFEITO DOS ADSORVENTES INTESTINAIS DE PECTINA/ MONTMORILLONITA EM PARÂMETROS BIOQUÍMICOS DO SANGUE DURANTE O TRATAMENTO CRÔNICO COM ÁCIDO ACETILSALICÍLICO**EFFECT OF PECTIN/MONTMORILLONITE INTESTINAL ADSORBENTS ON BLOOD BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS DURING CHRONIC TREATMENT WITH ACETYLSALICYLIC ACID****ВЛИЯНИЕ КИШЕЧНЫХ АДСОРБЕНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ПЕКТИН/МОНТМОРИЛЛОНИТА НА БИОХИМИЧЕСКИЕ ПАРАМЕТРЫ КРОВИ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ АЦЕТИЛСАЛИЦИЛОВОЙ КИСЛОТЫ**

KAPYSHEVA, Unzira^{1*}; BAKHTIYAROVA, Sholpan²; ZHAKSYMOV, Bolatbek³; SMAGULOVA, Zuchra⁴; TALGATOV, Eldar⁵

^{1,2,3} Institute of Human and Animal Physiology, Laboratory of Ecological Physiology, Kazakhstan

⁴ Institute of Human and Animal Physiology, Laboratory of Lymph Circulation, Kazakhstan

⁵ Sokolskiy Institute of Fuel, Catalysis and Electrochemistry, Laboratory of Organocatalysis, Kazakhstan

* Correspondence author
e-mail: kapysheva.ihap@bk.ru

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RESUMO

O tratamento crônico com medicamentos anti-inflamatórios não esteroides, como o ácido acetilsalicílico, pode causar vários efeitos adversos e condições crônicas. Os adsorventes intestinais à base de materiais naturais são utilizados para prevenir ou tratar várias intoxicações. Neste estudo, foi descrita a desintoxicação e o efeito protetor de adsorventes intestinais compostos de pectina / montmorillonita em ratos que receberam altas doses de ácido acetilsalicílico. 60 ratos Wistar receberam 100 mg / kg de ácido acetilsalicílico sem ou juntamente com adsorventes intestinais compostos à base de montmorillonita e pectina a 5%, 10% e 20%. Após 16 dias de experimento, amostras de sangue foram coletadas para medir os perfis bioquímicos do sangue, incluindo níveis de proteína total, albumina, glicose, colesterol e enzimas hepáticas. Foram observadas mudanças significativas no perfil bioquímico do sangue e nos níveis de enzimas hepáticas em ratos que receberam ácido acetilsalicílico por 16 dias. A administração concomitante de ácido acetilsalicílico e adsorventes intestinais compostos à base de montmorillonita e pectina a 5%, 10% e 20% proporcionou um efeito protetor, julgado pela recuperação da bioquímica sanguínea e dos perfis de enzimas hepáticas para controlar os níveis. O adsorvente composto com pectina a 20% teve efeito máximo. Portanto, os adsorventes intestinais pectina / montmorillonita podem ser utilizados para diminuir a irritação gastrointestinal e os efeitos adversos de medicamentos, como o ácido acetilsalicílico.

Palavras-chave: *pectina, transorbente, inflamatório, anti-inflamatórios não esteroides.*

ABSTRACT

Chronic treatment with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs such as acetylsalicylic acid may cause a number of adverse effects and chronic conditions. Intestinal adsorbents based on natural materials are used to prevent or treat various intoxications. In this study, it was described detoxification and protective effect of composite pectin/montmorillonite intestinal adsorbents in rats receiving high doses of acetylsalicylic acid. 60 Wistar rats received 100 mg/kg of acetylsalicylic acid without or together with composite intestinal adsorbents based on montmorillonite and 5%, 10%, and 20% pectin. After 16 days of the experiment, blood samples were collected to measure blood biochemistry profiles, including levels of total protein, albumin, glucose, cholesterol and liver enzymes. It was observed significant changes in blood biochemistry profile as well as in liver enzyme levels in rats receiving acetylsalicylic acid for 16 days. Concomitant administration of acetylsalicylic acid and composite intestinal adsorbents based on montmorillonite and 5%, 10%, and 20% pectin provided a protective effect as judged by recovery of blood biochemistry and liver enzyme profiles to control levels. The composite

adsorbent with 20% pectin had maximum effect. Therefore, pectin/montmorillonite intestinal adsorbents can be used to decrease gastrointestinal irritation and adverse effects of drugs, such as acetylsalicylic acid.

Keywords: *pectin, tagansorbent, inflammation, non-steriod anti-inflammatory drugs.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Хроническое лечение нестероидными противовоспалительными препаратами, такими как ацетилсалициловая кислота, может вызвать ряд побочных эффектов и хронических состояний. Кишечные адсорбенты на основе натуральных материалов используются для профилактики или лечения различных интоксикаций. В этом исследовании мы описываем детоксикационный и защитный эффект кишечных адсорбентов пектина / монтмориллонита у крыс, получающих высокие дозы ацетилсалициловой кислоты. 60 крыс линии Вистар получали 100 мг / кг ацетилсалициловой кислоты без или вместе с кишечными композитными адсорбентами на основе монтмориллонита и 5%, 10% и 20% пектина. После 16 дней эксперимента отбирали образцы крови для измерения профилей биохимии крови, включая уровни общего белка, альбумина, глюкозы, холестерина и ферментов печени. Мы наблюдали значительные изменения в биохимическом профиле крови, а также в уровне ферментов печени у мышей, получавших ацетилсалициловую кислоту в течение 16 дней. Одновременное введение ацетилсалициловой кислоты и кишечных композитных адсорбентов на основе монтмориллонита и 5%, 10% и 20% пектина обеспечивало защитный эффект, судя по восстановлению биохимических показателей крови и профилей ферментов печени до контрольных уровней. Композитный адсорбент с 20% пектина имел максимальный эффект. Вывод: кишечные адсорбенты пектин/монтмориллонит могут быть использованы для уменьшения раздражения желудочно-кишечного тракта и побочных эффектов лекарств, таких как ацетилсалициловая кислота.

Ключевые слова: пектин, тагансорбент, воспалительные, нестероидные противовоспалительные препараты.

1. INTRODUCTION

Acetylsalicylic acid (ASA, aspirin) is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) which acts through inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis. High-dose (more than 345 mg/day) ASA is used in clinical practice to treat fever, inflammation or pain. Chronic low-dose (75–325 mg/day) ASA therapy is a standard strategy to prevent the formation of blood clots and often used in patients after a heart attack or stroke (ATT Collaboration, 2009). Long-term treatment with NSAIDs often results in a chronic suppression of prostaglandin synthesis which leads to systemic and local adverse effects. Chronic ASA therapy often causes gastrointestinal symptoms (Iwamoto, 2013). According to the survey of patients treated with chronic low-dose ASA, 15% of patients suffered upper gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms, 70% being heartburn and/or eructation (Cayla, *et al.*, 2012). These symptoms are primarily caused by local epithelial reactions to ASA as this drug can potentially decrease the hydrophobic properties of epithelium and cause gastric mucosal damage. Additionally, ASA has a low pKa, which contributes to topical gastroduodenal damage (Sostres and Lanas, 2011). GI symptoms may occur due to inflammation-induced oxidative stress (Konturek *et al.*, 2010). Some patients

treated with ASA have lower GI symptoms such as minor bleeds, which may cause iron deficiency anemia and protein loss (Fortun *et al.*, 2005). These symptoms can be reversed by a cessation of ASA treatment, however, the risk-benefit assessment demonstrates the benefit of chronic ASA treatment especially in preventing cardiovascular diseases.

There is a number of strategies to reduce the risk of adverse effects related to NSAID treatment. The choice of strategy depends on associated risk factors such as gastric ulcers and *H. pylori* infection, elderly age, and concomitant medications. One of such strategies is the replacement of ASA with similar drugs (e.g. clopidogrel). However, these drugs have similar adverse effects on mucosa (CAPRIE Steering Committee, 1996). Additionally, drugs such as omeprazole and famotidine can be used to prevent gastric damage (Sostres and Lanas, 2011). However, concomitant use of these drugs can be more expensive compared to ASA monotherapy. This can be unsuitable for patients in countries with low-income economies and/or undeveloped medical care system. Recent studies showed that melatonin and its precursor L-tryptophan may reduce mucosal damage in healthy volunteers, probably through their radical scavenging ability (Konturek *et al.*, 2010). The search for novel strategies to reduce the risk of

NSAID-related adverse effects continues.

Intestinal adsorbents are candidate protective agents that reduce GI mucosa damage. Adsorbents based on kaolin, diosmectite and other clay minerals are used in traditional and evidence-based medicine as a supportive aid in acute diarrhea treatment (Pérez-Gaxiola *et al.*, 2015; Zaid *et al.*, 1995). Clay minerals are known to adsorb heavy metal ions, bacteria and mycotoxins *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Drucker *et al.*, 1977; Kang *et al.*, 2016; Uddin, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017). Administration of diosmectite showed an anti-inflammatory effect in induced colitis in rats, probably due to its ability to adsorb luminal antigens, increase of colonic mucin levels and possibly directly modulates cytokine production by mucosal cells (González *et al.*, 2004). Furthermore, diosmectite improves intestinal barrier function in pigs (Hu *et al.*, 2013).

Clay minerals can be modified by organic polymers to produce composite adsorbents with desired sorption properties (Alcântara *et al.*, 2014). Previously, it had been synthesized and characterized pectin-montmorillonite composite intestinal adsorbent which has shown the detoxifying ability in rats after cobalt salts intoxication (Talgatov *et al.*, 2016). Tagansorbent is a sorbent based on unmodified montmorillonite from Tagansky deposit (Kazakhstan). It is a health supplement used topically or orally in patients with acute diarrhea, heartburn and bloating (Mukovozova, 2010; <http://www.aptekar.kz>). Pectins are plant polysaccharides and main components of plant cell walls. They are derived from fruit and vegetable pulp and used widely in food, biomedical, and pharmaceutical industry. In the colon, pectins act as prebiotic agents. They are fermented by bacteria into butyrate known to inhibit colon inflammation (Wicker *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, pectins reduce glucose and cholesterol levels in blood probably due to their reduced adsorption. Pectin administration was shown to increase the urinary excretion of toxic metals such as arsenic and cadmium. However, the mechanism remains unknown as pectin is not soluble in the GI tract and does not adsorb in blood (Eliaz *et al.*, 2006).

Naturally occurring materials may be promising components for the development of adsorbents with detoxification properties. Additionally, the use of locally sourced materials may decrease the cost of drugs and health supplements making them accessible to patients.

In this study, it was explored the effect of

intestinal adsorbents based on apple pulp pectin and montmorillonite from Tagansky deposit (Kazakhstan) against adverse events related to ASA treatment.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Animals

60 Wistar rats of 220±10 g body weight were randomized into 5 groups. GI inflammation was provoked by ASA administration per os. ASA was purchased from OAO "Borisovskiy zavod medicinskikh preparatov" (Belarus). ASA dose was determined experimentally as 100 mg/kg or 20 mg/day per animal. Rats were treated for 16 days.

All animals except control group received 0.5 ml ASA per os and suspension of pectin/montmorillonite intestinal adsorbents (Pc/TS) with 5%, 10%, and 20% pectin. Pc/TS dose was 28.6 mg/kg (daily dose 6.3 mg). Control animals received 0.5 ml of water per os. Groups were assigned as follows: Group 1 (control) (n=12); Group 2 (n=12) – ASA solution; Group 3 (n=12) – ASA + Pc (5%)/TS; Group 4 (n=12) – ASA + Pc (10%)/TS; Group 5 (n=12) – ASA + Pc (20%)/TS.

The study was performed in compliance with the decision of the local ethical committee (Abstract of meeting #4, Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University, 09 Apr. 2018).

2.2. Preparation of composite intestinal adsorbents

Pectin was isolated from 'Golden delicious' apples. Apples were pulpified, the resulting pulp was dried at room temperature and milled. Pectin isolation and preparation of composite intestinal adsorbents were performed as described in (Talgatov *et al.*, 2016). Starting material was placed in a stainless steel reactor followed by the addition of citric acid solution (pH 1.4). The mixture was stirred continuously for 4 hours at 80°C. pH was corrected to 3.4 using sodium hydroxide solution. Pectin was precipitated by adding ethanol and separated using vacuum filtration. The precipitate was washed and air-dried in ambient conditions. To obtain solutions with 5%, 10%, 20% pectin was dissolved in water at 60°C and then added to montmorillonite (tagansorbent from Taganskiy deposit, Kazakhstan) suspension (1 g clay in 15 mL water). The solution was stirred for 2 h at ambient temperature and then kept in mother liquor for 16 h. Solids were washed with water

and air-dried.

2.3. Blood biochemistry and liver enzyme profiles

After 16 days of the experiment, blood samples were collected by decapitation. Fresh blood was stabilized with heparin (2-3 U/ml) and centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 15 min. Serum supernatant was collected and used for further analysis. Levels of total protein, albumin, glucose, cholesterol, alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase was detected using A-25 automatic analyzer (BioSystems, Spain) and the respective reagent kits. Results were compared to the control group and group 2.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel. All data obtained from the experiment are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Differences between groups were calculated using unpaired Student's t-test and $p \leq 0.05$ were considered significant.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Blood samples from rats after 16 days of concomitant ASA and pectin/montmorillonite administration were analyzed. In the control group, total protein, albumin, glucose, and cholesterol serum levels were within the normal physiological range (Table 1). In contrast, we observed changes characteristic for inflammation processes in blood samples from animals receiving 20 mg/day ASA for 16 days. It is known that a decrease in total blood protein level and serum albumin levels are characteristic for liver and lower GI tract disorders (Danilova, 2003). Total protein and albumin levels in blood decreased by 10% and blood glucose and cholesterol levels increased by 18-20% and 10-11%, respectively.

The same parameters were studied in animals receiving ASA and composite intestinal adsorbents with various pectin concentrations. In animals receiving Pc/TS with 5% pectin (group 3), we observed a 4-5% decrease of total protein level and 3-4% increase of serum cholesterol level compared to control animals. However, these animals maintained elevated glucose level. Total protein levels, albumin, glucose and cholesterol levels in animals receiving Pc/TS with 10% pectin (group 4) were similar to the control group (Table 1). Correspondingly, animals

receiving Pc/TS with 20% pectin (group 5) had biochemical profile similar to untreated animals. Interestingly, the mean cholesterol level in this group was significantly lower compared to the control group (Table 1).

Elevated levels of serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and alkaline phosphatase (AP) indicate increased hepatocyte membrane permeability and are considered is an indicator of acute liver damage (Danilova, 2003). Normally, ASA does not induce liver damage. However, it was sought to analyze ALT, AST, and AP levels in treated animals. In animals receiving only ASA (group 2), it was observed an increase of ALT levels by 20% and AST levels by 40-45% (Table 2). AP concentration increased 2.2-fold compared to control group.

In animals receiving Pc/TS with 5% pectin, ALT and AST levels were higher compared to the control group (4% and 9%, respectively). Administration of intestinal adsorbents did not change serum AP levels. After administration of intestinal adsorbents with 10% pectin (group 4), ALT and AST levels were restored to normal values, however, AP level was 25% higher compared to control (Table 2).

Animals receiving intestinal adsorbents with 20% pectin demonstrated maintenance of normal ALT and AST levels. Additionally, we found that the mean AP level of AP in this group was significantly lower compared to other groups (Table 2). This demonstrates an evident gastroprotective effect of pectin.

It was demonstrated that administration of high-dose ASA for 16 days leads to dramatic changes in biochemical and enzymatic profiles of treated animals. Total blood protein levels increased by 10%, serum liver enzyme levels (ALT, AST, and AP) increased by 20%, 40%, and 220% respectively. These changes are related to liver dysfunction which may also occur in patients chronically receiving high doses of ASA. In rats receiving ASA and pectin/montmorillonite adsorbents, we observed that the decrease of liver enzyme serum levels was in direct relationship to the increase of pectin concentrations. Therefore, pectin/montmorillonite intestinal adsorbents can be used to prevent drug-induced liver injury in patients receiving drugs which may cause liver damage.

Similarly to liver enzyme levels, a decrease of glucose and cholesterol levels in rats receiving ASA and Pc/Ts intestinal adsorbents was in direct relationship to the increase of pectin

concentrations. These findings corroborate the results of other studies showing lower cholesterol levels in subjects receiving pectin as a food supplement (Leclere *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, we assume that the components of the intestinal adsorbent used in this study retain their properties and function. Clay minerals are able to bind drug substances in vitro affecting drug release but not adsorption of the drug (Mináriková *et al.*, 2017; Djebbi *et al.*, 2018). Therefore we suggest that the composite mineral adsorbent acts through binding with ASA. Similar properties were shown for pectin (Bermúdez-Oria *et al.*, 2018). The pectin component of the composite intestinal adsorbent probably decreases ASA absorbability and correspondingly its systemic exposure and effect. However, it remains unknown whether the detoxification effects are more evident for pectin alone or as a component of the intestinal adsorbent. Moreover, there is a need in experiments accessing ASA pharmacokinetics after administration of individual components of the composite intestinal adsorbent.

Use of composite intestinal adsorbents as food supplements can be an effective strategy to reduce the rate of adverse effects during ASA treatment. This is particularly important as ASA and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs are one of the most prescribed medications particularly to elderly patients (Wongrakpanich *et al.*, 2018). Results of this study can be used to develop and more advanced intestinal adsorbents based on naturally occurring materials and investigate their mechanism of action.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

This study described the effect of composite pectin/montmorillonite intestinal adsorbents on blood biochemical parameters during chronic treatment with ASA. It was demonstrated that intestinal adsorbents with 20% pectin have maximum protective effect. Results of this study can be used to develop effective strategies to reduce adverse effects in patients receiving non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and other medications.

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6. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS:

ASA – acetylsalicylic acid; NSAID – non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug; GI – gastrointestinal; Pc/TS – pectin/montmorillonite (Tagantsorbent) based intestinal adsorbent; ALT – alanine aminotransferase; AST – aspartate aminotransferase; AP – alkaline phosphatase.

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Table 1. Effect of composite intestinal adsorbents on blood total protein level, serum albumin level, glucose and cholesterol levels in rats after ASA and Pc/TS administration

No.	Group	Parameter			
		Total protein (g/L)	Albumin (g/L)	Glucose (mmol/L)	Cholesterol (mmol/L)
1	Control	63.3±0.02	29.33±1.02	3.62±0.02	2.61±0.002
2	ASA	57.33±0.03*	25.74±1.42*	4.29±0.004*	2.84±0.004*
3	ASA + Pc (5%)/TS	60.99±0.04*	30.82±2.00*	4.45±0.002*	2.68±0.003*
4	ASA + Pc (10%)/TS	63.19±0.01*	29.90±1.29*	3.54±0.003*	2.51±0.005*
5	ASA + Pc (20%)/TS	63.55±0.01*	28.76±0.66*	3.55±0.003*	2.19±0.006*

* – p ≤ 0.05 compared to group 1.

Table 2. Effect of composite intestinal adsorbents on serum liver enzymes level in rats after ASA and Pc/TS administration

No.	Group	Parameter		
		ALT (unit/L)	AST (unit/L)	AP (unit/L)
1	Control	63.3±0.02	29.33±1.02	3.62±0.02
2	ASA	57.33±0.03*	25.74±1.42*	4.29±0.004*
3	ASA + Pc (5%)/TS	60.99±0.04*	30.82±2.00*	4.45±0.002*
4	ASA + Pc (10%)/TS	63.19±0.01*	29.90±1.29*	3.54±0.003*
5	ASA + Pc (20%)/TS	63.55±0.01*	28.76±0.66*	3.55±0.003*

* – $p \leq 0.05$ compared to group 1.